

HRM PRACTICES IN READY-MADE GARMENTS SECTOR IN BANGLADESH: PERCEPTIONS OF EMPLOYEES ABOUT TRAINING FACILITIES

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Abstract:

Human resource management practices in ready-made garments sector has been a widely research area for years. But unfortunately, there have been no sufficient numbers of studies conducted on this area in the context of Bangladesh although ready-made garments sector is part of a rich industry in Bangladesh. Training is a major function of HRM. This study was undertaken to identify and to clarify ins and outs of employee's perceptions about training facilities in the ready-made garments sector of Bangladesh. The analysis of the data collected from 5 ready-made garments companies in Bangladesh shows that there has no sufficient training opportunities. A survey has been conducted among 50 employees of different ready-made garments companies within Dhaka city by using a structured questionnaire and analyzed them objectively. Finally the study concludes that the concerned authorities should be aware about training of employees in order to improve the performance of employees as well as performance of the organization.

Keywords: HR practices, readymade garments, training, performance

1. Introduction

Ready-made garments (RMG) sector is the leading sector of Bangladesh in terms of women employment and foreign exchange earnings (Ali, 2008). So human resource practice is always a challenge for any RMG firm. To proper management of RMG employees of Bangladesh it needs to train-up them. The effectiveness of the employee performance is largely depends upon the human resource policy and practices (Storey, 1989). According to HR policy, there needs to sufficient training facilities of employees because training increases the skills, behavior of employees. Training facilities of RMG employees are not sufficient. Perception of employees about training is not positive. But

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training is a major function of HRM. Therefore, the management should consider to extent the training of employees.

2. Objectives of the Study

The main objectives of the study are to identify and to clarify the employee's perceptions about training facilities in the RMG of Bangladesh. Followings are the specific objectives of the study:

- to review the RMG sector;
- to identify and to clarify the training as a major function of HRM;
- to identify the perceptions of employees about training facilities;
- to identify different problem areas of this sector;
- to suggest some policy measures for solving the problem related to the RMG sector.

2.1 Scope of the Study

This study has focused upon the various problems regarding with the garments company and the prospect of these industries. We have taken 5 garments company to gather data on the present situation of the garments industries as well as problem regarding and the future of the industries.

This particular subject is extremely extensive in nature. This report tried to concentrate only on the training as a major function in RMG sector. This particular study is extremely extensive in nature. Hard effort was given to make the study worthwhile and meaningful; even then, there exists some limitations.

2.2 Limitation of the Study

Since our study is based on both primary and secondary data, there is a possibility of getting improper information. If the surveyed personnel provide us with any fabricated information about their opinion of their organization, then the report findings may be erroneous. Above all, this study is inaccurate in some points. The notable ones are as under:

- The survey was conducted in a very short time so I was not able to collect more information.
- Only the big and the reputed garments company consider here as sample.
- The questionnaire contains some questions that, if answered properly, might damage the company's image. In this type of questions, the respondents might provide socially acceptable answers. This risk was unavoidable.
- Another limitation of this study is the person's private information were not disclosing some, data and information for obvious reasons, which could be very much useful.
- Lack of experience in this field.
- Lack of proper authority to conduct the interview program.

3. Research Methodology

3.1 Sampling Plan

We visited different garments companies and the companies who intended to talk with us were taken as a sample. We tried to get rid of any kind of personal biasness and taking true information. 50 employees have been selected as study sample.

3.2 Data Collection

For the assessment, both primary and secondary data was collected. For this, we interviewed 5 garments companies through using a structured questionnaire. Personal interview technique was applied while fill up the questionnaire on respondents. The sample garments companies who are interviewed are given in a chart.

In Bangladesh, various RMG are available. To conduct the study researcher has selected five of them. The names of the selected Ready-made Garments are: BEXIMCO Fashions Ltd, Hamim Group, Fakir Group, DBL Group and Square Fashions Ltd.

3.3 Data Analysis and Representation

Using the necessary software package for Windows for example Microsoft Word, Microsoft Excel etc, carried out the report analysis and interpretation. I quantified my research through Likert scale and Weighted Average method. There is graphical representation given on the report. We used here-Scaling, Chart, Statistical formula, Tabulation etc.

4. Literature Review

Ready-made Garments industry of Bangladesh is well known industry in the world. Lots of research was conducted on various issues on this field. Basically about working conditions, industrial dispute, conflict, compliance issues etc. HRM practices are important issue on this field. There has god scenario of the RMG sector in respect to HR practice, working condition, job satisfaction revealed in many past research. Chowdhury and Protima Mazumdar (1991) and the Bangladesh Unnayan Parisad (1990) have studies on this topic. Both of these studies use accepted survey and research methodology to analyze a wealth of data on the social and economic background, problems and prospects of female workers in the RMG sector of Bangladesh. Female workers have a good contribution on this field. Quddus (2006) presents results from a survey of apparel entrepreneurs and evaluates the performance of entrepreneurs and their contribution to the success of this industry. Khan (2006) argued for strengthening social compliance issues and labor standards to improve wages, working hours, overtime, job security, the right to form trade unions, social security and also occupational health and safety. Azimet et al. (2010) were exploring the impact of HR practices on job satisfaction in the context of Bangladesh. It was found that HR practices have significant association with job satisfaction. In addition, Human Resource

Planning (HRP), and Training and Development were found to have positive impact on job satisfaction. Jakir (2010) said that demand of basic human needs have a great force the workers to follow the way of violent behavior. He compared life of prisoner and life of garment workers in Bangladesh. Rubel and Daisy (2013) identified the relationship between perceived supports and performance of workers. The study suggests that perceived organization supports are necessary for the sustainability of performance of workers in the RMG industry in Bangladesh. Sarker and Rumana (2014) examined the financial and non-financial incentives as motivational factors in order to keep job satisfaction of RMG workers of Bangladesh. This study shown that financial and non-financial factors can keep workers satisfied with their job and perceive workers to avoid industrial disputes. The study adopted regress method. Sabbir (2015) examined in his study whether the RMG sectors in Bangladesh follow the HRM rules and regulations. It also clarified either HRM is emphasized by RMG sectors in Bangladesh or not. Therefore, HRM practice of the RMG sector in the country have a great extend to study and training is focused on the study.

5. Conceptual Framework

Human resource management is a discipline and practice in the management of people in an organization, has evolved and developed into different areas. These practices have gone through a process of trial and error, theory building and testing of various concepts by practicing managers and academics (Farnham & Pimlott 1979; Storey 1989; Armstrong 1995). Training is a process whereby people acquire capabilities to aid in the achievement of organizational goals (Mathis & Jackson, 2003). So training is a major function of HRM. Employees should provide training facilities to achieve organizational goals.

6. Data Analysis and Findings

6.1 Descriptive Statistical Analysis

This section turns around analyzing the selected sample’s demographic characteristics like age, gender, educational qualification, marital status. The tables are in the below:

Table 1: Demographic information of the respondents

Particulars	Frequency	Percent
Age		
20-30	10	20.0
30-40	22	44.0
40-50	12	24.0
50-60	6	12.0
Total	50	100.0
Gender		
Male	22	44.0
Female	28	56.0

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Total	50	100.0
Marital status		
Unmarried	12	24.0
Married	38	76.0
Total	50	100.0
Educational qualifications		
SSC	20	40.0
HSC	5	10.0
BBA/Honors	10	20.0
MBA/Masters	15	30.0
Total	50	100.0

From the above table (table 1) we can see that most of the respondents are in the age of 30 to 40 (44%) years, more than half of the respondent are female (56%), most of them are married (76%) and 40% of respondents have the SSC degree.

6.2 Training as a Major Function of HRM: Measuring employee's perceptions

In this study, we try to evaluate the opinions level of the employees of Readymade Garments in Bangladesh. Here we have used closed ended question to identify the level of employee's opinions. Each question has analyzed with the help of likert scale method and statistical formula.

The likert's scale and assigned weight that has used for this study are given below:

Table 2: Likert's scale

Scale	Weight
Strongly Disagree	1
Disagree	2
Neutral	3
Agree	4
Strongly Agree	5

Formula used for weighted average:

$$X = \frac{\sum wx}{\sum w}$$

Where,

X = weighted average,

W = relative weight (%) and x= value.

Question 1: My organization arranges training program regularly

Table 2: Perceptions about training arrangement

Parameters	Percentile	Respondents	Product	WA
Strongly Disagree	10.0	05	05	0.72
Disagree	40.0	20	16	
Neutral	20.0	10	06	
Agree	30.0	15	09	
Strongly Agree	00.0	00	00	
Total	100.0	50	36	

Figure 1: Perceptions about training arrangement

It can be observed that the majority of the employees are disagreeing with the arrangement of training program. The weighted average here is 0.72, which means that the employees are close to strongly disagree with the arrangement of training program.

Question 2: The training is provided for long duration.

Table 3: Perceptions about training duration

Parameters	Percentile	Respondents	Product	WA
Strongly Disagree	40.0	20	04	0.45
Disagree	30.0	15	09	
Neutral	10.0	05	1.5	
Agree	20.0	10	08	
Strongly Agree	00.0	00	00	
Total	100.0	50	22.5	

Figure 2: Perceptions about training duration

It can be observed that the majority of the employees are disagreeing about longer duration of training program. The weighted average here is 0.45, which means that the employees are close to disagree on this issue.

Question 3: I have given trainings related to my job responsibilities and also which helps in my overall development.

Table 4: Perceptions about training participation

Parameters	Percentile	Respondents	Product	WA
Strongly Disagree	30.0	15	4.5	0.57
Disagree	40.0	20	16	
Neutral	20.0	10	06	
Agree	10.0	05	02	
Strongly Agree	00.0	00	00	
Total	100.0	50	28.5	

Figure 3: Perceptions about training participation

It can be observed that employees are disagreeing about the statement. The weighted average here is 0.57, which means that the employees are close to disagree in this issue.

Question 4: Training improves performance.

Table 5: Perceptions about training importance

Parameters	Percentile	Respondents	Product	WA
Strongly Disagree	00.0	00	00	3.27
Disagree	00.0	00	00	
Neutral	10.0	05	1.5	
Agree	10.0	05	2	
Strongly Agree	80.0	40	160	
Total	100%	50	163.5	

Figure 4: Perceptions about training importance

It can be observed that majority of the employees are agreeing about the statement. The weighted average here is 4.20, which means that the employees are usually to agree on this issue.

Question 5: The training programs are satisfactory of my organization.

Table 6: Perceptions about training availability in the organization

Parameters	Percentile	Respondents	Product	WA
Strongly Disagree	30.0	15	4.5	0.61
Disagree	40.0	20	16	
Neutral	20.0	10	06	
Agree	10.0	05	04	
Strongly Agree	00.0	00	00	
Total	100.0	50	30.5	

Figure 5: Perceptions about training availability in the organization

It can be observed that majority of the employees are disagreeing about the statement. The weighted average here is 0.61, which means that the employees are close to disagree with the statement.

7. Recommendations

In order to solve the problems that have been found in the study some measures can be taken for the surveyed factors. These can help in developing the performance of employees and can make a better environment for working in the organization.. To be an upper position holder in the world Garments Sector there is no way except follow the above recommendations. We hope by maintaining proper management and policy strategies our country will take the apex position in future.

1. Without the approval of the management, all your training designs would fail. Make sure the people at the top are aware of your training of employees and needs within the organization.
2. The training program should be arranged in a meaningful way so that it works for developing employees and it must be effective for the employees.
3. There should have a recognized training institution with extensive training facilities of each RMG organization.
4. Properly maintaining the database of employee training.
5. There should have training budget in the expense plan of RMG organization.
6. Build employees' competence and self-confidence through training, feedback and recognition.
7. Working environment makes a positive sense among the employees concept about the organization.

8. Conclusions

Although several studies have attempted to identify several HRM factors to determining overall organizational performance but this paper attempts to clarify the employee's perceptions about training facilities in RGM of Bangladesh aspect. It is concluded from the above discussion that majority of the respondents are female and their perceptions about training facilities in RMG of Bangladesh is negative. But success in the RMG largely depends on its training of employees. So the authorities and managers should be aware about employees training facilities in order to improve the performance of the organization.

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